

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Data Platform

M1.1 Annual Data Platform Meeting 2024

Tier: Technology

Priority Area: Data Platform ([2024-TECHNOLOGY-Data](#))

Executive Summary

The ELIXIR Data Platform held its annual hybrid face-to-face meeting in Padua, Italy. This provided a valuable opportunity to promote the Platform's objectives within ELIXIR's Scientific Programme for 2024–28 and foster collaboration between Work Packages.

Participants addressed important challenges such as how to properly credit contributions to databases, how to develop scalable approaches to data curation and how to implement FAIR-centric practices for data. Key discussions centred on the APICURON initiative, protocols for sharing multi-omics data (the MARS initiative), and establishing quality indicators for ELIXIR Community Databases.

On day one, the sessions focused on biocuration challenges, including balancing curator workload and submitter responsibility, and provided strategic updates on priority areas, including the Human Data and Translational Research, Cellular and Molecular Research, and Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens. Day two concentrated on external collaborations, particularly with the European Open Science Cloud, and explored accreditation frameworks beyond traditional publications.

The event produced tangible outcomes, including the development of a first draft list of indicators for database quality and a workshop proposal on metadata validation protocols and gamification elements to enhance community engagement with credit recognition platforms. The meeting successfully set the future direction of the Data Platform.

Full details of the Platform's activities and updated strategic direction are available in the D1.1 Annual Report 2024 (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15007351](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15007351)).

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Supporting Documents

D1.1 Annual report 2024 - Data Platform (ExCo, AHM, monthly meeting, ad-hoc meeting)

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Dissemination Plans

Zenodo upload and inclusion in ELIXIR Zenodo Community